

The DEMIX Wine Contest: a summary

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Abstract— The DEMIX ‘wine contest’ is a novel framework for a practical approach to inter-compare a range of candidate digital elevation models (DEMs) based on pre-defined criteria and a statistically sound ranking approach, known as the randomized complete block design (RCBD). The application of the ‘wine contest’ to six 1 arc-second global DEMs, considering a wide set of study sites, covering different morphological and landcover settings, highlights the potentialities of the approach. Results confirmed significant superiority of COPDEM and FABDEM over ALOS AW3D30, NASADEM, SRTM and ASTER GDEM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, several Earth observation missions have resulted in finer than 100m resolution global Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), most of which are shared freely and openly worldwide.

At this time, at least six different global medium resolution (i.e., 10-100m) DEMs have been produced using a variety of techniques. We expect more to come in the near future as new technologies and methods are developed. However, most users do not have the resources and expertise to perform an in-depth comparison of different DEMs. Therefore, expert advice that provides information pertinent to the user's need will benefit the community to identify the most appropriate dataset.

As a major step towards this goal, this paper presents the wine contest, a novel and flexible tool to provide geospatial data users with a practical approach to inter-compare a set of candidate global DEMs based on pre-defined criteria and a statistically sound ranking approach. The framework provides the wider geospatial community tailored recommendations regarding available DEM products that are not limited to one domain, geographic area, or landscape type. The method is flexible and customizable in relation to the specific needs and requirements of users in their particular application.

II. METHODS

Ranking a collection of wines or a set of DEMs from a given set of candidates leads to a mathematically similar problem. The method can also be applied to comparisons of other geospatial products and is in no way limited to ranking of global DEMs.

In a real wine contest, each expert or connoisseur judges the wine on its own merits which can be based on a set of criteria such as taste, colour, bouquet, price, etc. The judge(s) evaluate and build an opinion based on their experience and taste without knowing the origins of the wine. The overall winner is thus declared after considering all the opinions, with equal weight.

For the inter-comparison of global DEMs, it is necessary to produce the contest ranking based on evaluations of the DEMs against high accuracy data (high-resolution lidar DEMs, geodetic benchmarks etc). The evaluations can be qualitative (subjective based on the opinion of an expert) or quantitative, based on some objective method that can produce a numerical result, which is amenable to be sorted.

The DEMIX wine contest is prepared as an *evaluations table* of k columns and N rows recording the assessment outcomes for each of the candidate DEMs and an *opinions table*, which translates the evaluations table to ranked opinions. A hypothetical example of these tables is presented in Figure 1.

Criteria that in general cannot be ranked, i.e., whose results cannot be interpreted in the sense of better or worse, are not applicable to the wine contest. Ties, individual results which are considered equally good (or equally bad), can be considered by applying the mid-rank procedure.

Tolerances should account for measurement uncertainty to identify minor differences in the evaluations table that will have an impact in the opinions table but are not really different. For example, many of the global DEMs only record elevation to the nearest meter and thus differences of centimeters or even decimeters would not record a significant difference among them.

Assessments	Evaluations			Opinions				
	DEM-1	DEM-2	DEM-3	DEM-1	DEM-2	DEM-3		
Visual assessment of the hillshade (by Expert 1)	1	2	3	1	2	3		
Visual analysis of fine scale morphology (by Expert 2)	Fair	Very good	Bad	2	1	3		
ELVD_RMSE (tol=0.5m)	17.12	16.96	23.94	1.5	1.5	3		
ELVD_LE90 (tol=0.5m)	25.95	21.81	36.06	2	1	3		
ELVD_MAE (tol=0.5m)	10.47	12.89	16.77	1	2	3		
SLPD_RMSE (tol=0.5%)	17.27	14.17	20.73	2	1	3		
SLPD_LE90 (tol=0.5%)	23.11	16.34	30.34	2	1	3		
SLPD_MAE (tol=0.5%)	9.35	6.95	12.34	2	1	3		
				R_i	13.5	10.5	24.0	
				R_j^2	182.25	110.25	576.0	sum=868.5

Figure 1. A wine contest example applied to the inter-comparison of DEMs - the evaluations table (left side) records the assessment outcomes for each of the candidate DEMs. The opinions table (right side) translates the evaluations table to ranked opinions.

The null hypothesis in the context of this ‘wine contest’ means that there is no difference among the DEMs, and a consensus based on the opinions cannot be achieved. However, if the null hypothesis is rejected, then the contest ranking is not based on chance (given a chosen confidence level) and some conclusions can be obtained.

A statistical confidence must be associated to the final wine contest rankings because it is imperative that the outcomes produced are not due entirely to chance (as might happen if the opinions table rankings are taken naively).

One of the strengths of the wine contest is that both quantitative and qualitative evaluations can be integrated into the contest. Therefore, a non-parametric test should be used which can operate over both types of rank results. The chosen non-parametric test for the wine contest is the Friedman Test [1], because among the non-parametric choices at hand, it is the best alternative for minimizing the risk of paradoxical results.

The general Friedman's statistic χ_r , is presented in Eq.1, valid with or without ties (N =number of opinions/assessments, k =number of DEMs).

$$\chi_r^2 = \frac{N(k-1) \left[\sum_{j=1}^k \frac{R_j^2}{N} - C_F \right]}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^k r_{ij}^2 - C_F}; C_F = \frac{Nk(k+1)^2}{4} \quad (1)$$

To apply the Friedman Test the entries in the opinions table (Fig.1) are denoted as the elements r_{ij} , and the final row presents the column sums by R_j . The remaining values to compute the Friedman statistic (χ_r) can be extracted from the same table: with $C_F=96$, sum of $r_{ij}^2=111.5$, and sum of $R_j^2=868.5$, then $\chi_r=12.968$.

For a given k , N and confidence level alpha, the Friedman's statistic value χ^2 is compared to the critical value; if χ^2 is larger, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the conclusion is that we cannot accept that the DEMs are equivalent. Since we are willing to accept ties, the standard critical values tables from the Friedman Test are not suitable. From the table for $k=3$ provided by [2], and at the 95% confidence level, the row $N=8$ offers a critical value to compare of $\chi_{crit}=5.793$. Compared to the χ_r result of 12.968 which is larger, one should reject the null hypothesis that the opinions table entries are purely at random, implying that the DEMs are equivalent.

The null hypothesis has been rejected based on the Friedman Test, so there are statistically significant differences among the set of DEMs under consideration. The lower the values of R_j , the better, but it is still necessary to assess whether the difference between the pairs of ranked candidate DEMs are statistically significant, or otherwise conclude that the pair is tied. The process is denoted as post-hoc analysis and there exist different options to carry out such an analysis. In this case and following [3], we propose to use the test by [4] applying the Bonferroni correction.

A pair of DEMs is considered significantly different if

$$|R_i - R_j| \geq z_{1-\alpha/k/(k-1)} \sqrt{\frac{Nk(k+1)}{6}} \quad (2)$$

In this example, the critical value for the post-hoc analysis will be 4.005. To conclude whether there is a significant difference between ranked pairs the absolute difference between R_i and R_j should be greater than 4.005:

DEM3 vs. DEM2: $\text{abs}(24.0-10.5) = 13.5 \rightarrow$ significant

DEM3 vs. DEM1: $\text{abs}(24.0-13.5) = 10.5 \rightarrow$ significant

DEM1 vs. DEM2: $\text{abs}(13.5-10.5) = 3.0 \rightarrow$ not significant

From a DEM user perspective, the above wine contest results say that for the given assessment, either DEM1 or DEM2 could be equally recommended because there is no significant difference between them and they both ranked significantly better than DEM3 in the overall comparison. The conclusion is valid at the 95% confidence level.

III. GLOBAL DEMs COMPARISON

The wine contest approach was applied for the comparison of the six global DEMs that are available at a spatial resolution of 1" (ALOS AW3D30, ASTER GDEM, COPDEM, FABDEM, NASADEM, SRTM) using a variety of criteria. The method is based on four overall steps:

Step 1: Obtain high quality reference elevation data (data with significantly higher accuracy elevation measures and much smaller sampling spacing than the DEMs to be tested);

Step 2: Prepare *reference DEMs* from the reference data. If required, adjust the vertical datum of reference DEMs;

Step 3: Evaluate the reference and global DEM data, for every test area and for every criterion to produce the evaluations table (Fig.2);

Step 4: Rank the global DEMs according to the wine contest rules to produce the opinions table. Produce final rankings based on chosen statistical confidence levels.

Figure 2. A) Location of the 124 test areas. B) Distribution of DEMIX tiles over Las Palmas Island. The names of the test areas shown on the map A: 01 - Norway, 02 - Oxford, 03 - Caen, 04 - Valonne, 05 - Vanoise, 06 - Trentino, 07 - Pyrenees, 08 - Madrid, 09 - Ebro Delta, 10 - Almeria, 11 - Las Palmas, 12 - Canary East, 13 - Redwoods, 14 - State Line, 15 - Canyon Range, 16 - Republican River, 17 - Shenandoah, 18 - Blackwater, 19 - Chincoteague, 20 - Charleston, 21 - Pernambuco, 22 - São Paulo, 23 - Uruguay, 24 - La reunion.

For each test area where reference DEMs were available, one or more DEMIX sampling tiles were extracted. A DEMIX tile is an area covering approximately 10 km x 10 km in size and defined on a geographic latitude/longitude grid [5].

The preparation of the reference DEMs was performed in MICRODEM version 2023.2.5 [6]. Of the global DEMs under consideration, only FABDEM claims to be a DTM. The rest of the candidate global DEMs are closer to DSMs but most likely fall somewhere between a true DTM and DSM [7]. Due to this ambiguity, all the global DEMs considered were compared against both reference DTMs and DSMs when available. MICRODEM was used to produce a wine contest GIS database, combining the tile characteristics, the evaluations table, and an opinions table with an initial set of tolerances. The implemented DEMIX wine contest database [8] includes 39785 opinions which are rows found within the database.

For all DEMIX tiles the following parameters were computed: Elevation Differences (ELVD), Slope Differences (SLPD), Roughness Differences (RUFDD). The differences between the reference DEM and global DEM were always computed in the same manner:

$$difference = global_{DEM} - reference_{DEM}$$

where positive values indicate that the global DEM has a higher value than the reference DEM at a specific pixel.

For each parameter, the quantitative assessments were based on the following criteria: Standard Deviation (STD), Average Deviation (AVD), RMSE, MAE, LE90.

These quantitative assessments can be refined based on different slope and land cover classes:

- Cliff – pixels having a slope > 50%;
- Steep – pixels having a slope > 25% and < 50%;
- Gentle – pixels having a slope < 25% and > 12.5%;
- Flat – pixels having a slope < 12.5%.

The land cover classification used was the Copernicus Global Land Cover Layers – Collection 2 [9].

The final step in the DEMIX wine contest ranks of the candidate global DEMs. The functionality to read the database and implement the statistical procedures required to produce the final rankings was made available through a Jupyter notebook [10].

The information provided in the database allows the user to directly select opinions most appropriate to their requirements. For each run, the Jupyter notebook computes the final rankings based on the chosen opinions including the required confidence levels to support the outcomes. Furthermore, the DEMIX wine contest Jupyter notebook provides tools to analyse outputs by creating graphics and figures to help understand the final, wine contest rankings.

IV. RESULTS

Figure 3 summarizes the results of wine contests applied to subsets of the database. The top rows show the overall ranking using all tiles and criteria based on the DTM and DSM reference DEMs. For this set of evaluations (ALL land type), the DTM winner is FABDEM and the DSM is COPDEM, both at the 95% confidence level.

The DEMIX wine contest also associates statistical significance to the ranking and this is presented in Figure 3 by drawing a box around those global DEMs whose rank cannot be differentiated from a random result, i.e., the pairwise rank outcome does not pass the significance test.

The subsequent rows have been grouped by DTM or DSM, land type filter (FLAT, GENTLE, FOREST, etc), and criterion (ELVD_RMSE, SLPD_LE90, RUFD_MAE, etc). Not only the order can change but also the number of ties and between which candidate DEMs the ties have occurred. This illustrates the power of the wine contest procedure in the context of the inter-comparison of global DEMs because depending on the user requirements, the ‘best’ DEM will emerge based on the set of chosen criteria, far from a situation of one-option-fits-all.

To try and visualize the final ranking outcomes with a bit of context, Figure 3, columns B/D presents the same outcomes with the goal of showing how many times a DEM ranks higher/lower over the number of opinions. The output is the sum of the ranks for any particular DEM for each row in the opinions table divided by the number of opinions. The more times a DEM is ranked higher in the opinions table, the higher the ranking. In this case, lower is better.

To demonstrate the effects that changing tolerances can have on the final rankings, Figure 3B/D presents the outcomes based on higher tolerances: $0.5 \rightarrow 1.0$ and $0.2 \rightarrow 0.4$. The increasing of the tolerances has had the effect of producing more ties between the different global DEMs. This is an important result for the inter-comparison of global DEMs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the novel ‘DEMIX wine contest’, for the inter-comparison of digital elevation models which produces a final ranking with prescribed confidence levels based on given criteria. We applied the method to six global 1” DEMs: ALOS, ASTER, COPDEM, FABDEM, NASADEM, and SRTM. The inter-comparison was done using 15 criteria related to elevation, slope and roughness measures derived from reference 1” DEMs. The wine contest provides final rankings with confidence level based on the choice of criteria and land type which demonstrates

the powerful features of this method including the ability for the user to choose the most relevant criteria and areas.

From an overall final ranking of the global 1” DEM inter-comparison, COPDEM, ALOS and FABDEM are clearly the frontrunners based on the chosen criteria and test areas.

SRTM and NASADEM are distinctly in the lower half of the wine contest rankings indicating lower quality than the top three. If we limit ourselves to the tested criteria, the conclusion is that these global DEMs should no longer be used except perhaps to create composite DEMs or where elevations acquired around February 2000 are required.

As many prior studies have shown, the ASTER DEM is clearly the lowest performer and should only be used with great care when no alternatives exist.

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